

2-Hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone (Lapachol)—A New pH Indicator

S. S. SAWHNEY and (KM.) NEELAM VOHRA

Department of Chemistry, D.A.V. Post Graduate College, Dehradun (U.P.)

Manuscript received 9 June 1976, revised 18 September 1976, accepted 10 November 1976

2-Hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone has been successfully employed as a pH indicator in acidimetry and alkalimetry. With Lapachol, the pH range for colour change (yellow to wine-red) is 3.7 to 5.7, thereby, rendering it more suitable for acid-base titration as compared to phenolphthalein and methyl-orange.

THE role of naphthoquinone and its derivatives in the field of medicine, industry and complexometry is well documented¹⁻³. The behaviour of hydroxy naphthoquinone with the variation of pH is little explored. Sawhney and Trehan employed 5-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone successfully in acidimetry and alkalimetry as a pH indicator⁴.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of analytical grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water and standardised pH-metrically. For absorption measurements Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20, spectrophotometer was employed. Buffer solutions of Clark and Lubs were used⁵. For absorbance curves of lapachol, different sets with varying pH were prepared. Each set consisted of 0.2 ml (0.002M) lapachol and 5 ml buffer. Indicator was prepared by dissolving 0.480 g/litre in MeOH. Volumetric experiments were carried out in the usual way. Decinormal solutions excepting in the case of pyroborate ion where 0.2N solutions were used, were employed.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves for lapachol at a series of pH were obtained by plotting absorbance against wavelength (Fig. 1). It is seen that the absorbance at λ 490 nm, with increasing pH, increases. The isosbestic point appeared at λ 410 nm and which

FIG. 1.—Lapachol: Absorbance curves at various pH values.

confirms the presence of a system consisting of two chromophores. The colour change (yellow to wine red) is due to conversion of para quinonoid structure to ortho-quinonoid structure.

p-Quinonoid Lapachol anion. Yellow in acid condition.
o-Quinonoid. Wine-red in alkaline condition.

pK_{1n} of lapachol (4.7) was obtained by plotting absorbance against pH at λ 490 nm. A usual S-shaped curve is obtained.

Neutralisation of a strong acid with strong alkali and vice versa at laboratory temperature

Lapachol with colour change interval as pH ranging from 3.7 to 5.7 could be employed with encouraging results, in the titration of strong acid with strong base and vice versa. The supporting evidence was the coincidence of stoichiometric point and colour change during pH -metric titrations in the presence of indicator. For comparative study, the titration with phenolphthalein and methyl-orange were also carried out.

Excepting in alkalimetry in which analytical similarity exists, lapachol is more suitable in acidimetry as compared to phenolphthalein and methyl-orange. In HCl-NaOH titration, the relative error with phenolphthalein, methyl-orange and lapachol are 0.2, 0.2 and 0.2% with a standard deviation of 0.002 with lapachol. In acidimetry, the relative errors computed are 0.53, 0.66 and 0.28% with standard deviation of 0.003 with lapachol.

Neutralisation of ammonia, pyroborate ion (using borax) and carbonate with strong acid at laboratory temperature

The results obtained volumetrically using lapachol as an indicator are also quite encouraging. Even in pH -metric titration of ammonia, borate and carbonate with hydrochloric acid, in presence of indicator (Lapachol), the equivalence point and colour change, i.e., wine red to yellow coincided.

In carbonate-HCl titration, the relative error with phenolphthalein, methyl orange and lapachol are

3.0, 0.66 and 0.44% with standard deviation of 0.003 with lapachol where as in ammonia-HCl titration the relative error using methyl orange or lapachol is 0.2% and standard deviation with lapachol is 0.003.

Titration of hydrochloric acid with ammonia at laboratory temperature

While titrating 10 ml (0.1N) hydrochloric acid with 0.1N ammonia pH metrically in the presence of lapachol, the coincidence of end point and colour change, yellow to wine-red was observed. The relative errors computed using methyl orange and lapachol as indicators, are 0.28 and 0.26 percent respectively. The standard deviation computed is 0.002.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. P. K. Sharma for providing necessary facilities. Km. Neelam Vohra is also grateful to CSIR for a Junior Fellowship.

References

1. K. D. JAIN, A. K. JAIN, S. S. SAWHNEY and R. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 270.
2. K. D. JAIN, A. K. JAIN and R. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 552.
3. K. D. JAIN and S. S. SAWHNEY, *J. Sci. Res. (Hardwar, India)*, 1971, 3, 15; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, 80, 529114.
4. S. S. SAWHNEY and NARESH C. TREHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 295.
5. H. H. WILLARD, L. L. MERRITT and J. A. DEAN, "Instrumental Methods of Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., London, 1965, p. 607.